

MOTIVATIONAL FACTORS AND BEHAVIORAL INTENTION TO INVEST IN PHILIPPINE STOCK MARKET AMONG MILLENNIAL AND GEN-Z INVESTORS IN CALAMBA CITY

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the motivational factors influencing the behavioral intentions of Millennial and Gen-Z investors in the Philippine stock market, specifically within Calamba City. The research focused on understanding financial knowledge, financial well-being, overconfidence bias, and investment risk within these generational groups, providing valuable insights for financial institutions, regulators, and market participants seeking to engage this demographic in the equity market. Utilizing the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) as a framework, the study investigated how various motivational factors shaped the key TPB components: attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control. By employing this approach, the research aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the behavioral intentions of Millennial and Gen-Z investors in the stock market. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed, collecting data through surveys from 265 randomly selected respondents. The collected data underwent thorough statistical treatment for analysis and evaluation. The findings revealed consistent agreement among participants regarding key motivational factors, indicating a low positive correlation toward behavioral intention for investing but highlighting a gap between financial aspirations and current financial status. While there were variations in overconfidence bias and investment risk perception among Millennial and Gen-Z investors, a common understanding prevailed regarding financial knowledge and financial well-being. These insights led to the development of a proposed strategic investment action plan, including the implementation of targeted educational programs and communication campaigns designed to address the identified gap, enrich understanding,

enhance engagement, and promote long-term participation of this demographic in the Philippine Stock Market.

Keywords: *Stocks, Philippine Stock Market, Millennial, Gen-Z, Motivational Factors, Behavioral Intention*

INTRODUCTION

The stock market plays a pivotal role in the development of a country's industry and commerce, which has a significant impact on its economy. This significance extends to both the industry and the investors, which is why the government and even the central banks of a particular country keep a close eye on what is happening in the stock market.

The Millennial generation has emerged as the largest labor force, most populous, most educated, and most diverse generation. They are known for their unique attitudes, preferences, and technological competence, and they have brought about significant changes in various aspects of society, including investment behavior. Some Millennials are now in their highest earning years, giving them more money to invest and save for their own financial goals. As a result, the future of the investing business may be strongly impacted by their financial choices. Eventually, the market's future will depend on Millennial investors to continue further economic growth (Goldman Sachs, 2023).

Furthermore, Generation Z, representing the newest wave of investors, is growing up in an era defined by technological advancements, widespread access to information, and global connectivity. They have been shaped by the rise of social media, instant communication, and an increased emphasis on social responsibility. These factors contribute to a distinctive set of attitudes and preferences when it comes to financial decision-making, including their approach to investing in the stock market (Goldman Sachs, 2023; Deloitte, 2022).

The Philippine stock market, as a vital component of the country's economy, offers Millennials and Gen Z investors a platform to participate in wealth creation and long-term financial growth. Traditionally, trading stocks posed challenges for young individuals, requiring visits to libraries or financial advisors and direct contact with brokers. However, the advent of the internet and technological advancements have revolutionized stock trading. The younger generation who is more familiar with technology and social media, finds it easier to access information and engage in online trading platforms (Central Bank of the Philippines, 2021).

As a result of technology's low entry barriers, more people have been encouraged to start investing. The 2021 Financial Inclusion survey conducted by the Central Bank of the Philippines reveals that investment ownership has increased to 36% of the total adult population in 2021 from 25% in 2019. However, only 1% of adults have investments in equity securities such as stocks, Unit Investment Trust Fund (UITF), and mutual funds.

Various constraints contribute to this low percentage, including job insecurity, perceived high costs, lack of awareness, and low trust in investment providers (Central Bank of the Philippines, 2021).

While most Filipinos invest with the primary objective of protecting themselves against emergencies and achieving life goals, a smaller percentage holds investments specifically for retirement preparation and asset accumulation. Unfortunately, research indicates that financial literacy among young adults in the Philippines is lacking, with many individuals lacking a fundamental understanding of financial concepts. Despite these limitations, recent studies suggest that Filipino Millennials show behavioral intentions and take the initiative to invest in order to achieve financial security, particularly in response to the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic (Deloitte, 2022).

Notably, domestic investors, particularly young, low-income Filipinos seeking higher returns, have made significant contributions to the trading volumes on the Philippine Stock Exchange (PSE). This increased participation has led to the establishment of more stock market accounts. However, despite these positive trends, there are still obstacles that hinder the ability of Millennials and Gen Z investors to save and invest effectively. Furthermore, limited research exists on the specific factors that motivate them to engage in the Philippine stock market. (Philippine Daily Inquirer, 2021).

This study examined the key motivational factors, including preferences and knowledge related to stock market investments, which influence the behavioral intentions of Millennial and Gen Z investors in the Philippine stock market. The investigation adopted the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), which suggested that behavioral intention is shaped by attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control (Ajzen, 1991). By exploring these motivational factors within the framework of TPB, the study provided a comprehensive understanding of the underlying drivers behind Millennial and Gen Z investors' behavioral intentions.

By uncovering the extent to which motivational factors drive the behavioral intention of Millennial and Gen Z investors to participate in the Philippine stock market, the main purpose of this study was to contribute to the existing literature on investment behavior and provide valuable insights for financial institutions, regulators, and market participants. The outcomes facilitated the development of targeted strategies, educational programs, and communication campaigns aimed at enhancing the understanding, engagement, and long-term participation of Millennials and Gen Z individuals in the stock market. The study attempted to create an action plan aimed at further enhancing the motivation and behavioral intention of Millennial and Gen Z investors in Calamba City to participate in the Philippine Stock Market.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to investigate the motivational factors and behavioral intentions of Millennial and Gen Z in Calamba City regarding their investment in the Philippine Stock Market. The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent are motivational factors to invest in Philippine Stock Market observed as assessed by Millennial and Gen Z Investors in Calamba City in terms of:
 - 1.1 Financial Knowledge,
 - 1.2 Financial Well-being,
 - 1.3 Overconfidence Bias, and
 - 1.4 Investment Risk?
 2. What is the level of behavioral intention to invest in Philippine Stock Market as assessed by Millennial and Gen Z Investors in Calamba City in terms of:
 - 2.1 Attitude,
 - 2.2 Subjective Norm, and
 - 2.3 Perceived Behavior Control?
 3. Is there a significant difference between the assessment of the Millennial and Gen Z Investors as to extent of observance of motivational factors and the level of behavioral intention to invest in Philippine Stock Market?
 4. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of observance of motivational factors and the level of behavioral intention to invest in Philippine Stock Market as assessed by Millennial and Gen Z investors in Calamba City?
 5. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan may be proposed?
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METHODOLOGY

The methodology of the study is presented in this section. The discussion includes the research design, research locale, population and sampling, respondents of the study, research instrument, validation of the instrument, data gathering procedure, and treatment of quantitative data. Ethical considerations are also addressed to ensure the trustworthiness and dependability of the study.

Research Design

The research design encompassed the overall strategy or plan that outlined the approach and methods used to conduct the research study. The descriptive-correlational method of research was chosen as the research design to understand and describe the relationship between motivational factors and behavioral intention among Millennial and Gen Z investors in the Philippine stock market. This research design enabled the collection of data that described the variables of interest and explored the associations or correlations between them. Descriptive analysis was utilized to depict the current state of the identified variables, while correlational analysis was employed to assess the strength of the relationship between the identified motivational factors and the level of behavioral intention to invest in the Philippine stock market, using statistical data.

Additionally, McCombes (2020) suggested that the purpose of adopting the descriptive correlational method was to identify and describe the inherent variables and correlations. This process entailed gathering data related to specific groups or circumstances. To collect the necessary data, a survey questionnaire was utilized, and individual data were obtained using the descriptive correlational method.

Research Locale

The research was conducted at Laguna College of Business and Arts, Calamba City, Laguna, with the criteria of those who already graduated in college from 2000 to 2023, and with the consideration that respondents who belong to these criteria were respondents who could be classified as Millennial and Gen Z generation. They were chosen as the respondents because LCBA's role as a pioneering institution in providing quality education in Calamba City aligned well with the research focus. The college attracted individuals who had pursued higher education, making them more likely to have the necessary knowledge and interest in financial matters, including stock market investment. Conducting the research at Laguna College of Business and Arts provided convenient access to a pool of potential participants who met the criteria. The institutional support accelerated the data collection process and contributed to the overall success of the study.

Population and Sampling

This study utilized a simple random sampling technique based on the sampling frame, which included Millennial and Gen Z investors in Calamba City who had graduated from Laguna College of Business and Arts between 2000 to 2023. The sampling was established with an effect size of .20 to quantify the magnitude of the difference between populations, a margin of error of .05, and a confidence level of .95, calculated with the expertise of the researcher's statistician using the G*Power. Of the 7,364 population of LCBA graduates from 2000 to 2023, a total of 260 (3.5% of the total number) participants were selected as respondents.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were Millennial and Gen Z participants in Calamba City who graduated from LCBA between the years 2000 and 2023. The sample was selected specifically to capture the perspectives and experiences of this demographic group. In this study, respondents included both current investors and individuals who had not yet invested in the Philippine Stock Market. This approach aimed to provide valuable insights into their motivations, attitudes, and perceptions that might have influenced their behavioral intentions and future investment decisions.

Table A

Respondents of the Study

TYPE OF RESPONDENT	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Millennials	130	50%
Generation Z	130	50%
Total	260	100%

The specific number of respondents was shown in Table A and it was determined in consultation with a statistician, considering factors such as confidence level, margin of error, expected effect size, and data variability. The group of respondents included one hundred thirty (130) Millennial and Gen Z participants.

Instrument

The research instrument was proposed to be an adopted instrument that had been used in previous studies and had demonstrated reliability and validity. It consisted of three parts, each containing several questions related to specific variables. The first part of the questionnaire assessed the Investor Profile, gathering information about the participants' demographic and background characteristics. The second part focused on measuring the motivational factors associated with investing in the Philippine stock market, including financial knowledge, financial well-being, overconfidence bias, and investment risk. The third part evaluated the participants' level of behavioral intention to invest in the stock market, examining Attitude, Subjective Norm, and Perceived Behavior Control.

To capture responses and measure the dimensions being assessed, a four-point Likert scale was employed. This allowed participants to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement with each statement. The application of the Likert scale in this study was further explained with an interpretation as shown below.

Mean-score Interval and Verbal Interpretation on the Extent of Observance of Motivational Factors as assessed by Millennial and Gen Z Investors in Calamba City

Ranges of Mean	Rating	Categorical Response	Verbal Interpretation
3.25 - 4.00	4	Strongly Agree	Fully Observed
2.50 - 3.24	3	Agree	Observed
1.75 - 2.49	2	Disagree	Partially Observed
1.00 - 1.74	1	Strongly Disagree	Not Observed

Mean-score Interval and Verbal Interpretation on the Level of Behavioral Intention to invest in the Philippine Stock Market

Ranges of Mean	Rating	Categorical Response	Verbal Interpretation
3.25 - 4.00	4	Strongly Agree	With Full Intention
2.50 - 3.24	3	Agree	With Intention
1.75 - 2.49	2	Disagree	With Partial Intention
1.00 - 1.74	1	Strongly Disagree	No Intention at all

Validation of the Instrument

Cronbach's Alpha for the independent variable (motivational factors) was adopted from the research by Yang et al. (2021), resulting in Cronbach's Alpha values: Financial Knowledge - 0.861, Financial Well Being - 0.890, Overconfidence Bias - 0.920, and Investment Risk - 0.894, while the dependent variable (behavioral intention) came from Schmidt (2010), yielding: Attitude - 0.945, Subjective Norms - 0.950, and Perceived Behavioral Control - 0.946. All values met the reliability threshold (>0.70), affirming satisfactory content validity.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data collection for this study primarily relied on a survey questionnaire administered to the target respondents. The questionnaire served as the main source of primary data that is designed to collect data on the variables of interest, such as motivational factors and behavioral intentions. To ensure the accuracy, completeness, and authenticity of the instrument, the assistance of a statistician and the research adviser was sought. Their expertise was instrumental in refining the questionnaire.

Treatment of Quantitative Data

For the analysis of the quantitative data collected from the Millennial and Gen Z investor respondents, the following statistical treatments will be applied:

1. When describing the level of the motivational factors and the level of behavioral intention among Millennial and Gen Z investors, the Mean and a four-point Likert scale were both employed.
2. To determine if there was a significant difference between the assessment of Millennial and Gen Z investors regarding the extent of observance of motivational factors and the level of behavioral intention to invest in the Philippine Stock Market, independent t-tests were used.
3. The strength and direction of the relationship between motivational factors (independent variable) on the level of behavioral intention (dependent variable) among Millennial and Gen Z investors were measured using the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient.

Scope and Delimitation

This study assessed the extent of observance of motivational factors and the level of behavioral intention to invest in the Philippine Stock Market among Millennial and Gen Z investors in Calamba City. The variables examined in assessing the extent of observance of motivational factors among Millennial investors included financial knowledge, financial well-being, overconfidence bias, and investment risk. The

determinants used in assessing behavioral intention were attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control, based on the Theory of Planned Behavior model.

The study adopted a quantitative approach to describe the relationship between the extent of observance of motivational factors and the level of behavioral intention to invest in the Philippine Stock Market. Descriptive statistics were employed to summarize and describe the data, while correlation analysis was used to examine the relationship between the variables.

The study adhered to ethical guidelines, ensuring participant confidentiality, voluntary participation, and informed consent. The respondents of the study were limited to Millennial investors born between 1981-1996 and Gen Z investors born between 1997-2012 in Calamba City, Laguna, Philippines. The findings may not be generalizable to Millennial and Gen Z investors in other cities or regions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered from the surveyed questionnaire with the application of the appropriate statistical tools.

Table 1.1

Extent of Motivational Factors to Invest in the Philippine Stock Market observed as assessed by Millennial and Gen Z Investors in Calamba City in terms of Financial Knowledge

Indicators in terms of Financial Knowledge	Gen Z		Millennials		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
1. I have complete knowledge of the Philippine stock exchange	2.76	O	2.54	O	2.65	O	3
2. I checked the financial statements of the company for the past 5 years before investing in the Philippine stock exchange	2.38	PO	2.68	O	2.53	O	4
3. I consider the financial position of a company before investing in the Philippine stock exchange	2.92	O	2.98	O	2.95	O	1
4. Considering a long-term period (e.g., 10–20 years) stocks normally give the highest return	2.75	O	3.04	O	2.90	O	2
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	2.70	O	2.81	O	2.76	O	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Fully Observed (FO)
2.50 – 3.24 Observed (O)

1.75 – 2.49 Partially Observed (PO)
1.00 – 1.74 Not Observed (NO)

Financial Knowledge was Observed (2.76) by Millennial and Gen Z Investors in Calamba City as to the extent of motivational factors to invest in the Philippine stock market. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Observed. Furthermore, the indicator “I consider the financial position of a company before investing in the Philippine stock exchange” got the highest mean of 2.95, while the indicator “I checked the financial statements of the company for the past 5 years before investing in the Philippine stock” got the lowest mean of 2.53.

It can be concluded that LCBA graduates observe financial knowledge and demonstrating a positive mindset toward investing in the Philippine Stock Market. This indicates a foundation of financial literacy among the surveyed group, providing a basis for making well-informed decisions and potentially participating in the stock market in the future with a strategic and wise approach.

To support the study, Barber and Odean (2019) explored the impact of financial education on individual financial behavior. The study suggested that financial education had a significant and positive impact on individual financial behavior. Participants who received financial education demonstrate greater financial knowledge and make more informed investment performance compared to individuals who did not receive financial education.

According to the research conducted by Aguirre et al. (2021), students with higher financial literacy were more likely to perceive stock market investments and express a greater intention to invest. Financial literacy acted as a motivational factor by enhancing students' understanding of investment opportunities and reducing perceived barriers related to affordability.

Furthermore, Junaeni (2020) claimed that investors must know and understand which type of investment was most appropriate for them so that they are not easily trapped by exaggerated investments. Once investors chose the type of investment, they must also be able to evaluate the level of return and risk they face to avoid losses. Hence, the investment decision may vary depending on investors understanding and perception.

Financial Well-being was Observed (2.83) by Millennial and Gen Z Investors in Calamba City as to the extent of motivational factors to invest in the Philippine stock market. Notably, they were “securing their financial future” (highest mean of 3.35) while the indicator they are “behind with their finances” (lowest computed composite mean of 2.58). Motivational factors to invest in the Philippine Stock Market was observed as assessed by Millennial and Gen Z Investors in Calamba City in terms of Financial Well-being.

Table 1.2

Extent of Motivational Factors to Invest in the Philippine Stock Market observed as assessed by Millennial and Gen-Z Investors in Calamba City in terms of Financial Well-being

Indicators in terms of Financial Well-being	Gen Z		Millennials		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
1. I am securing my financial future	3.29	FO	3.40	FO	3.35	FO	1
2. I am behind with my finances	2.70	O	2.45	PO	2.58	O	5
3. My finances control my life	2.67	O	2.58	O	2.63	O	4
4. I am just getting by financially	2.76	O	2.74	O	2.75	O	3
5. I am concerned that the money I have or will save won't last	2.97	O	2.73	O	2.85	O	2
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	2.88	O	2.78	A	2.83	O	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Fully Observed (FO)
2.50 – 3.24 Observed (O)

1.75 – 2.49 Partially Observed (PO)
1.00 – 1.74 Not Observed (NO)

It can be deduced that LCBA graduates demonstrate a strong dedication to long-term financial planning and security. Despite this commitment, there appears to be a gap between their aspirations for financial well-being and the current reality of their financial circumstances, leading to challenges in securing their financial obligations and goals.

While they currently manage their finances, there is a sense that they are not thriving or attaining the level of financial security they aspire to achieve and although they can meet their basic needs, there is a noteworthy absence of substantial financial flexibility. Additionally, a prevailing concern among these graduates revolves around the durability of their savings and whether it will prove adequate for their future needs.

It is consistent with the findings of Koekemoer and Ferreira (2019) who explained that financial well-being encompasses a distinctive perspective, extending beyond mere financial considerations. It is linked to various aspects of an individual's life, such as psychological adjustment, physical health, and life satisfaction, which evolve throughout the investor's life cycle.

Moreover, Shahnaz et al. (2019) examined the financial well-being across three different level income groups in Malaysia. The study's key finding revealed a notable trend within the low-income group, where individuals experienced heightened levels of financial stress and reported the lowest levels of financial satisfaction compared to counterparts in higher-income groups.

Notably, Khalil and Akhtar (2019) underscored that investors who exhibit positive investment behaviors can reap substantial benefits, particularly in terms of their overall financial well-being which aligned with the broader understanding that prudent financial choices contributed significantly to an individual's financial health.

pessimism, stock market returns tended to be lower, affecting the profitability of investments.

Furthermore, Qasim et al (2019) concluded that overconfidence leads to an overestimation of the actual performance of securities. Economic theories suggested that investors should be rational and consider all available information before making decisions. However, in reality, due to the overwhelming amount of information, investors often resort to shortcuts in decision-making. Overconfidence prompted investors to take more risks, and decisions based on overconfidence are often irrational. When making investment decisions, an overconfident investor relied on personal beliefs rather than thoroughly evaluating all available information, resulting in decisions that may not be rational.

Similarly, Arquero et al. (2019) examined the stock market participation among students in the Philippines. The study revealed that students with more confidence and positive attitudes toward investing were more likely to participate in the stock market

Table 1.4

Extent of Motivational Factors to Invest in the Philippine Stock Market observed as assessed by Millennial and Gen-Z Investors in Calamba City in terms of Investment Risk

Indicators in terms of Investment Risk	Gen Z		Millennials		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
1. I consider myself a high-risk taker	2.61	O	2.93	O	2.77	O	5
2. If I unexpectedly received some easy money, I would surely invest a certain amount of money in stocks	2.88	O	3.18	O	3.03	O	2
3. I would prefer to invest in stocks rather than to keep money in a bank account	2.91	O	3.48	FO	3.20	O	1
4. I consider risk in investments as an opportunity	2.58	O	3.31	FO	2.95	O	3
5. In the investment process, if it happens, I would not mind losing some money	2.68	O	2.88	O	2.78	O	4
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	2.73	O	3.15	O	2.94	O	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Fully Observed (FO)
2.50 – 3.24 Observed (O)

1.75 – 2.49 Partially Observed (PO)
1.00 – 1.74 Not Observed (NO)

Investment Risk was Observed (2.94) by Millennial and Gen Z Investors in Calamba City as to the extent of motivational factors to invest in the Philippine stock market. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Observed. Furthermore, they “prefer to invest in stocks rather than to keep money in a bank account” (highest computed composite mean of 3.20) meanwhile, the indicator they “consider themselves as a high-risk taker” (lowest computed composite mean of 2.77). This indicates that the motivational

factors to invest in the Philippine stock market was observed as assessed by Millennial and Gen Z Investors in Calamba City in terms of Investment Risk.

It can be surmised that Millennial and Gen Z investors at LCBA have a positive inclination toward investing in the Philippine Stock Market. This inclination is highlighted by a strong preference for allocating their funds into stocks rather than keeping them in a traditional bank account. The surveyed participants also express a willingness to invest unexpected money in stocks and maintain a mindset that remains undeterred by potential losses in the investment process. The results portray an optimistic sentiment among the surveyed investors or potential investors, with a significant emphasis on the attractiveness of stocks as an investment option. The participants' readiness to view risk as an opportunity and their openness to investing even in the face of potential losses further accentuate their positive outlook on participating in the Philippine Stock Market. This collective attitude indicates a broader trend among Millennial and Gen Z investors at LCBA, reflecting a readiness to confront the challenges and uncertainties inherent in stock market investments.

Grable et. al (2020) provided evidence to support the findings, by mentioning the “reflection effect” which meant that decision-makers must choose between options with gains and losses, the preference for positive outcomes often mirrored the preference for negative outcomes.

To emphasize, Bejano and Capistrano (2021) identified different dimensions of risk that influence Filipino youth investors’ motivation to invest, including financial risk, psychological risk, and information risk. Youth investors who perceived these risks as manageable and acceptable were more likely to engage in stock market investments. It also highlighted the importance of financial knowledge and experience in shaping youth investors' risk perception and behavior. Participants with higher financial knowledge and previous investment experience exhibit a more informed and cautious approach toward investment risks. They were more likely to conduct thorough research, diversify their portfolios, and make risk-conscious decisions.

Table 2.1
Level of Behavioral Intention to Invest in the Philippine Stock Market as assessed by Millennial and Gen-Z Investors in Calamba City in terms of Attitude

Indicators in terms of Attitude	Gen Z		Millennials		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
1. I have a positive attitude towards Investing in the Philippine stock market	3.01	I	2.98	I	3.00	I	4
2. I believe that investing in stocks is important to achieve my financial goals	3.17	I	3.16	I	3.17	I	1
3. I have a favorable opinion of the potential benefits of stock market investments	2.94	I	3.12	I	3.03	I	2

4. I perceive investing in the stock market as a beneficial activity	3.00	I	3.03	I	3.02	I	3
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.03	I	3.07	I	3.05	I	
Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 With Full Intention (FI)			1.75 – 2.49 With Partial Intention (PI)				
2.50 – 3.24 With Intention (I)			1.00 – 1.74 No Intention at all (NI)				

Attitude revealed an Intention (3.05) to invest in the Philippine stock market as assessed by Millennial and Gen Z Investors in Calamba City. All indicators were verbally interpreted as With Intention. Furthermore, they believe that “investing in stocks is important to achieve my financial goals” (highest computed mean of 3.17). Meanwhile, they “perceive investing in the stock market as a beneficial activity” (lowest computed composite mean of 3.02). Millennial and Gen Z Investors in Calamba City in terms of attitude had intention to invest in the Philippine stock market.

It can be deemed from the findings that the tables reveal a robust acknowledgment of the importance of stocks in fulfilling financial objectives among the surveyed Millennial and Gen Z LCBA graduates. This strong acknowledgment is reflected in their favorable opinions regarding the potential benefits of stock market investments which collectively contributes to the positive attitude observed in this group.

This positive inclination is fundamental in comprehending the behavioral intentions of these investors. It indicates willingness among the surveyed individuals to actively participate in stock market activities as a strategic component of achieving their overall financial goals. The data highlights not only a positive attitude toward investing but also an understanding among Millennial and Gen Z LCBA graduates of the instrumental role stocks play in realizing their financial aspirations. Moreover, it underscores their readiness to embrace the potential advantages and challenges associated with engaging in the stock market as part of their broader financial planning.

Mahardhika & Zakiyah (2020) cited that Attitude towards investment behavior had a positive effect on a person to respond constantly to an investment intention. Attitude toward a behavior was determined by a person’s principles about behavior and subjective assessment of their own understanding and the environment around them. This was done by associating certain behaviors with the several strengths or weaknesses of the principles that can be obtained when the individual does or does not do them.

Comparatively, Smith & Johnson (2019) mentioned the influence of attitude on Millennials' intention to invest in the stock market. Through a survey of Millennial investors, the study collected data on participants' attitudes toward stock market investment and their intentions to invest. The findings suggested that Millennials with more positive attitudes toward stock market investment are more likely to express a strong intention to invest. The study emphasized the importance of cultivating positive attitudes toward stock market investment among this demographic.

Chen et al. (2020) also examined the relationship between attitude towards stock market investment and behavioral intention among Generation Z investors in China. The findings of the study indicated a positive relationship between attitude towards stock market investment and behavioral intention among Generation Z investors. In other

words, individuals who held more positive attitudes towards stock market investment were more likely to express a higher intention to invest in the stock market..

Table 2.2

Level of Behavioral Intention to Invest in the Philippine Stock Market as assessed by Millennial and Gen-Z Investors in Calamba City in terms of Subjective Norm

Indicators in terms of Subjective Norm	Gen Z		Millennials		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
1. Most people that are important to me, also invest in the Philippine stock market themselves	2.04	PI	2.06	PI	2.05	PI	3
2. Most people that are important to me, regard Philippine stock market investment as positive	2.70	I	2.61	I	2.66	I	2
3. Most people whose opinion I highly respect, would approve and recommend me to invest in the Philippine stock market	2.99	I	3.01	I	3.00	I	1
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	2.58	I	2.56	I	2.57	I	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 With Full Intention (FI) 1.75 – 2.49 With Partial Intention (PI)
2.50 – 3.24 With Intention (I) 1.00 – 1.74 No Intention at all (NI)

Subjective Norm revealed an Intention (2.57) to invest in the Philippine stock market as assessed by Millennial and Gen Z Investors in Calamba City. Furthermore, participants indicated that “most people whose opinion are highly respected would approve and recommend them to invest in the Philippine stock market” (highest computed composite mean of 3.00). Meanwhile, the indicator “most people important to them also invest in the Philippine stock market themselves” (lowest computed composite mean of 2.05). Millennial and Gen Z Investors in Calamba City in terms of subjective norms have intention to invest in the Philippine stock market.

It can be concluded that respected individuals play a crucial role in influencing the intention to invest among the surveyed participants. This emphasizes the importance of their social approval in shaping the decision-making process regarding stock market investment. However, a contrasting perspective emerges, evident in the lowest mean for the indicator related to the actual investment involvement of the important individuals themselves in the Philippine stock market. This indicates a potential disparity between the intention to invest and the real investment practices of individuals considered important by the participants.

This discrepancy can be attributed to various factors such as individual risk tolerance, financial circumstances, or differing views on the perceived benefits and risks of stock market investment. Understanding this is crucial for devising targeted strategies that align individual intentions with the influence of respected figures in the decision-making process. It highlights the need for interventions that address the potential misalignment and encourage a more coherent and collective approach to stock market investment within this demographic.

Considering the data presented above, Raut et.al. (2018, as cited in Bihari et al., 2022) found that subjective norms had a favorable relationship with the intention to invest. Subjective norms became a basis of the social influences of social circles that were influential in shaping someone's attitude (i.e., family and friends). The more hype or popular the investment product/ stock in his social group, the higher the probability of an investor buying or investing in it. Those significant referents were crucial in decision-making because investors found the acceptance of other's decisions, even though the investment is risky.

Another key point, Scandroglio (2019, as cited in Shin et al. 2019) mentioned was that the subjective norm was not significantly linked to the investor's intention to invest. This disconnect was attributed to the personal nature of financial dealings, where individuals may not be significantly persuaded by societal expectations or norms. Especially when it comes to stock market investments, people care more about their values, how much risk they can manage, and their unique situations rather than conforming to external societal expectations. Some people also depended on others' perceived trading knowledge when investing in the stock market, which may or may not motivate them to invest. This underscored the intricate and multifaceted nature of factors influencing investors' intentions in the dynamic landscape of financial markets.

Table 2.3

Level of Behavioral Intention to Invest in the Philippine Stock Market as assessed by Millennial and Gen-Z Investors in Calamba City in terms of Perceived Behavioral Control

Indicators in terms of Perceived Behavioral Control	Gen Z		Millennials		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
1. I feel very confident to be able to engage in Philippine stock market investing	2.90	I	2.82	I	2.86	I	1
2. I am capable of selecting stock	2.75	I	2.61	I	2.68	I	3
3. I understand and can easily follow the development of stocks	2.75	I	2.69	I	2.72	I	2
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	2.80	I	2.71	I	2.76	I	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 With Full Intention (FI)
2.50 – 3.24 With Intention (I)

1.75 – 2.49 With Partial Intention (PI)
1.00 – 1.74 No Intention at all (NI)

Perceived Behavioral Control revealed an Intention (2.76) to invest in the Philippine stock market as assessed by Millennial and Gen Z Investors in Calamba City. All indicators were verbally interpreted as With Intention. Furthermore, the surveyed participants “feel very confident to be able to engage in Philippine stock market investing” (highest computed composite mean of 2.86). Meanwhile, the indicator they are “capable of selecting stock” (lowest computed composite mean of 2.68). Millennial and Gen Z Investors in Calamba City in terms of perceived behavioral control had intention to invest in the Philippine Stock Market.

The overall positive inclination, with all indicators, suggests that Millennial and Gen Z investors in Calamba City feel motivated and confident about engaging in the Philippine stock market. This reflects a notable level of self-assurance among participants which is a positive indicator, as confidence is a key factor in encouraging individuals to take active steps in investment activities. Although the indicator "I am capable of selecting stock" had the lowest mean, it still falls within the intention range. This suggests that while participants express a degree of confidence, there might be a slightly lower perceived capability in the specific task of stock selection, and addressing these perceived limitations could further enhance their overall preparedness and efficacy in stock market participation.

Warsame & Ireri (2018, as cited in Hapsari 2020) mentioned that the perceived behavior control had a significant connection with the investing intention. Mindfulness, skill, experience, and capital affect people in the investment behavioral process. Investors who had longer exposure to investment activities became more inclined and that would lead to positive behavioral intention.

Correspondingly, Praja et al. (2020, as cited in Kusuma et al. 2020) defined intention as an individual's desire, either immediate or long-term, to undertake a given activity. In their study, Ejigu and Filatie (2020) explored the variables of investment intention in micro and small firms among business students in their study. According to the study's findings, financial literacy, perceived behavioral control, projected return, attitude, perceived trust, and perceived risk were significant predictors of students' propensity to engage in micro and small businesses.

Also worth mentioning, Ruby et al. (2019) mentioned the perception of ease or difficulty in carrying out an action that reflected experiences experienced. They claimed that if the investor thought that an action is easy to do without any significant obstacles, the individual immediately manifested the intention to take an action or behavior to be realized.

Table 3.1
Test of Significant Difference on the Assessment of the Millennial and Gen Z as to the Extent of Observance of Motivational Factors to Invest in the Philippine Stock Market

Sub-variables			Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F Ratio	Sig.	Remarks	Decision
Financial Knowledge	Between	Groups	.727	1	.727	1.689	.195	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Within	Groups	111.074	258	.431				
	Total		111.801	259					
Financial Well-being	Between	Groups	.650	1	.650	3.192	.075	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Within	Groups	52.539	258	.204				
	Total		53.189	259					
Overconfidence Bias	Between	Groups	1.388	1	1.388	3.947	.048	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Within	Groups	90.762	258	.352				
	Total		92.150	259					

Investment Risk	Between Groups	11.550	1	11.550	22.250	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Within Groups	133.927	258	.5199				
	Total	145.478	259					

Level of significance 0.05

There was a significant difference between the responses of the Millennial and Gen Z respondents regarding the specified variables. The test of significant difference had a probability value, overconfidence bias and investment risk of .048, and .000, respectively. These values were both less than the level of significance of 0.05, thus, rejecting the null hypothesis. Meanwhile, it was determined that there was no significant difference in financial knowledge and financial well-being in the assessment of their observance of motivational factors for investing in the Philippine stock market. The computed probability values for financial knowledge and financial well-being were 0.195 and 0.075, respectively. This suggested that in the context of observing motivational factors for investing in the Philippine stock market, there was no statistically significant difference between the Millennials and Gen Z regarding their financial knowledge and financial well-being.

In a study conducted by Riska (2020), she mentioned that there was no significant difference in motivation between these two generational cohorts implied that, according to the study's measured parameters, Millennial and Gen Z exhibited similar levels of drive or incentive when it comes to making decisions about investments. This lack of significant difference in motivation suggests a certain degree of uniformity in the factors driving individuals from Generation Z and Millennials to engage in investment activities.

Table 3.2

Test of Significant Difference on the Assessment of the Millennial and Gen Z as to the Level of Behavioral Intention to Invest in the Philippine Stock Market

Sub-variables		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F Ratio	Sig.	Remarks	Decision
Attitude	Between Groups	.127	1	.127	.185	.667	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	177.010	258	.686				
	Total	177.137	259					
Subjective Norm	Between Groups	.022	1	.022	.053	.818	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	108.093	258	.419				
	Total	108.115	259					
Perceived Behavior Control	Between Groups	.584	1	.584	.873	.351	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	172.514	258	.669				
	Total	173.098	259					

Level of significance 0.05

There was no significant difference in the attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavior control of the Millennial and Gen Z investors as to the level of behavioral intention to invest in the Philippine stock market. It had probability values of 0.667, 0.818, and 0.351, respectively. This suggested that in the context of the level of behavioral intention to invest in the Philippine stock market, there was no statistically significant difference between Millennial and Gen Z Investors.

Rizaldy (2020) investigated the generational effects of financial literacy and investment experience were analyzed within both groups. According to the findings, the mean for investment decisions among Millennials was slightly higher than that of the Generation Z group, indicating a tendency for Millennials to prioritize socially responsible investments. These inclinations could impact the observation and interpretation of motivational factors. Moreover, Rizaldy highlighted that the generational group cannot serve as an independent variable directly influencing investment decisions. However, when the generational group controlled financial literacy and financial behavior, the impact of financial literacy and financial behavior becomes more evident.

Table 4

Test of Significant Relationship between the Extent of Observance of Motivational Factors and the Level of Behavioral Intention to Invest in the Philippine Stock Market as assessed by Millennial and Gen Z Investors in Calamba City

Extent of Observance of Motivational Factors	Behavioral Intention	r value	P value	Remarks	Decision
Financial Knowledge	Attitude	.298**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Subjective Norm	.172**	.004	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Perceived Behavior Control	.254**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Financial Well-being	Attitude	.312**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Subjective Norm	.217**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Perceived Behavior Control	.292**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Overconfidence Bias	Attitude	.139**	.009	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Subjective Norm	.253**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Perceived Behavior Control	.351**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Investment Risk	Attitude	.207**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Subjective Norm	.372**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Perceived Behavior Control	.290**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀

**Correlational at the level 0.01

*Correlational at the level 0.05(Two-tailed)

There was a significant relationship between the extent of observance of motivational factors and the level of behavioral intention as evidenced by the r values ranging from .172 to .372 interpreted as Low Positive Correlation. The computed probability values .000, .004, and .009 were less than the level of significance ($P < 0.05$); thus, rejecting the null hypothesis.

It can be concluded that the extent of observance of motivational factors has a significant relationship with the level of behavioral intention to invest in the Philippine stock market as assessed by Millennial and Gen Z Investors in Calamba City. The higher the observance of motivational factors, the higher the behavioral intention. When the observation of motivational factors increase, behavioral intention also increases.

Several researchers, including Aren and Aydemir (2015, as cited in Sumiati et al., 2021), verified the significant positive effect of motivational factors on stock market investment intention. They argued that individuals with higher financial literacy were more

likely to express a greater intention to invest. Both basic and advanced financial knowledge showed a positive and significant effect on the intention to invest in risky instruments. The impact of financial literacy, including both subjective and objective aspects, also yielded significant results on the intention to participate in the stock market.

According to Yang et al. (2021), insignificant effects of financial well-being and financial literacy on stock market investment intention but confirmed the significant effect of Motivational Factors for Investment Risk and Overconfidence bias on stock market participation.

Table 5
The Proposed Action Plan

MAIN GOAL: To enhance the motivation and the behavioral intention of Millennial and Gen Z investors in Calamba City to invest in the Philippine Stock Market

KEY AREAS	OBJECTIVES	STRATEGIES/ ACTIVITIES	FREQ- UENCY	PERSONS INVOLVED	SUCCESS INDICATORS
Develop educational initiatives and financial workshops	To enhance financial literacy, investment knowledge, and the understanding of stock market dynamics to empower investors with the modern tools to make informed decisions.	Conduct regular financial literacy seminars; Develop online courses on investment basics and stock market dynamics.	Quarterly seminars	Financial experts and educators	Increased participation in seminars and collect feedback from at least 90% of participants. Attain at least 20% growth in the Millennials and Gen Z investors.
	To provide workshops that focused on practical financial management, budgeting, and goal setting, providing tools and strategies to help Millennials and Gen Z investors align their financial goals with their investment decisions	Conduct in-person or virtual workshops on financial management. Provide tools and templates for setting financial goals.	Quarterly financial planning workshops	Financial planners and advisors. Workshop facilitators.	Increased participation in workshops and collect feedback from at least 90% of participants. Attain at least 20% growth in the investors that will be profitable in the stock market investing
	To foster a sense of community among Millennial and Gen Z investors in Calamba City through events, forums, and networking opportunities.	Organize an investment-themed events and meet-ups.	Quarterly networking sessions. Annual investment-themed events.	Community managers. Guest speakers and mentors.	Achieve at least 20% increase in online community membership, measured by engagement metrics.
Community Engagement and Peer Networks:	To build a supportive investment community within Calamba City that can contribute to shared knowledge, investment experiences, and encouragement, to invest in the Philippine Stock Market.	Establish an online forum or social media group for discussions.	Regular community meetings. Annual recognition events.	Community leaders and moderators. Guest speakers for knowledge-sharing.	Achieve at least 20% increase in online community membership and collect feedback from at least 90% of the member community.
Partnerships with Local Institutions:	To collaborate with local educational institutions, community organizations, and businesses that support financial education and investment initiatives to reach a wider audience and create a more	Forge partnerships with schools for financial literacy programs. Collaborate with local businesses for sponsorship or support.	Annual financial literacy campaigns in schools. Regular business	Education coordinators. Business development team.	Increase participation and successful partnerships with at least 20% of local businesses, and ensure a 90% satisfaction rate for

Conclusions

Based on the research findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. That Millennial and Gen Z LCBA graduates consistently observed and displayed agreement in the motivational factors to invest in Philippine Stock Market in terms of Financial Knowledge, Financial Well-being, Overconfidence Bias, and Investment Risk. This indicates that LCBA graduates exhibit an active engagement in financial knowledge, demonstrating a positive attitude towards investing in the Philippine Stock Market. The collective results underscore their strong dedication to long-term financial planning and security. However, despite this commitment, a gap exists between their aspirations for financial well-being and the current financial circumstances, posing challenges in meeting obligations and goals. Millennial and Gen Z LCBA graduates display notable self-assurance in independently assessing securities prices, but with limited capacity to surpass market performance, emphasizing the importance of shaping educational efforts and support programs to enhance decision-making abilities and foster a well-rounded approach to stock market participation. Additionally, their favorable attitude towards risk and willingness to invest unexpected money in stocks reflect a mindset and eagerness to invest in the Philippine stock market.

2. That Millennial and Gen Z LCBA graduates have positive intention to invest in Philippine Stock Market in terms of Attitude, Subjective norms, and Perceived Behavior Control. Their preference for allocating funds to stocks, positive attitude towards risk, and willingness to invest even in the face of potential losses underscore their overall optimistic outlook. This collective attitude suggests a broader trend among LCBA's Millennial and Gen Z investors, indicating a readiness to navigate challenges in stock market investments. Also, respected individuals play a crucial role in influencing investment intentions, emphasizing the significance of social approval in decision-making. However, a notable contrast emerges, revealing a potential misalignment between the intention to invest and the actual investment practices of influential individuals. Despite this discrepancy, the overall positive inclination among participants indicates a reasonable motivation and confidence in engaging in the Philippine stock market. The slightly lower perceived capability in the specific task of stock selection, suggests room for improvement. Addressing these perceived limitations could further enhance overall preparedness and efficacy in stock market participation, building on the existing notable level of self-assurance.

3. That Millennial and Gen Z investors differ significantly in their tendencies related to overoptimism and their perception of risks associated with investing in the Philippine Stock Market, but they indicate a shared understanding or approach to financial knowledge and well-being, emphasizing commonalities between the two generations in these particular domains. Regarding the level of behavioral intention to invest in the

Philippine Stock Market, Millennial and Gen Z investors share similar intentions and perspectives.

4. That if the investors exhibit higher levels of observance in motivational aspects such as financial knowledge, financial well-being, overconfidence bias, and investment risk their behavioral intentions to invest also tend to increase.

5. That the proposed action plan is necessary to further enhance the motivation and the behavioral intention of Millennial and Gen Z Investors in Calamba City to invest in the Philippine Stock Market.

Recommendations

From the above conclusions, suggestions and recommendations were listed below:

1. To develop and implement educational programs that specifically target the identified gap in this study between aspirations for financial well-being and current financial status among Millennials and Gen Z investors in Calamba City. Programs may be provided to focus on practical financial management, budgeting, and goal setting. The community can collaborate with local educational institutions, financial experts, and industry professionals to organize workshops, seminars, and mentorship programs.

2. Recognizing and addressing the influence of family and colleagues on the investment decisions of Millennials and Gen Z investors in Calamba City, the community may collaborate with financial experts or successful investors to create awareness campaigns, specifically targeting those who may influence the investment decisions of Millennials and Gen Z investors, utilize various communication channels, including local media, social media platforms, and community events to disseminate information about the importance of making informed and consistent investment decisions.

3. To establish partnerships with local bank or financial institutions to create accessible and tailored financial products specifically designed for Millennial and Gen Z investors in Calamba City, they may work with these institutions to offer a range of investment options for each generational group with varying risk levels, ensuring alignment with the risk tolerance and financial goals of the youth demographic.

4. To prioritize the development of tailored educational programs that focus on improving financial knowledge, financial well-being, and the understanding of overconfidence bias and investment risks, these programs may be designed to be interactive, incorporating real-world scenarios and practical insights as they directly impact the confidence and intentions of Millennial and Gen Zs to invest in the Philippine Stock Market focusing on this motivational factor will empower investors by providing them with the necessary knowledge and skills to make informed decisions.

5. To implement a feedback mechanism to gather insights from Millennial and Gen Z investors on the effectiveness of the proposed action plan and to regularly assess

educational, support programs, and make necessary adjustments based on feedback, the community may organize feedback sessions, focus groups, or online forums to facilitate open communication and ensure that future initiatives are refined based on the evolving needs and challenges faced by the Millennial and Gen Zs.

6. There is a clear scarcity of literature on the subject. It is recommended that further research on motivational factors and behavioral intentions to invest in the Philippine Stock Market among Millennials and Gen Z may be conducted. Specific areas of investigation, such as exploring the impact of modern technology or examining the role of social media in shaping investment decisions to contribute valuable insights to the existing body of knowledge may be focused on.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical consideration was among the most crucial aspects of the research. Before proceeding with the data collection process, consent or ethical approval from the respondents was obtained to guarantee that the study adhered to ethical guidelines. In line with ethical research practices and to ensure transparency, attempts were made to contact the author for permission to adopt their instrument, yet no response was received. Throughout the research process, utmost care was taken to preserve the privacy and security of the information, ensuring the responsible and respectful conduct of the study.

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